

COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AND ITS ANALYSIS IN DIFFERENT VIEWS OF LINGUISTICS

¹Turdimatova Madinakhan Ravshanovna

ESL teacher of English language and literature department, Fergana State University turdimatovam@mail.ru,

²Khamrakulova Ravshanoy Abdulakhatovna

ESL Teacher of Applied and Natural Sciences, Correspondence Course Fergana State University ravshanoyhamrakulova@gmail.com
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854885>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th April 2023

Accepted: 21th April 2023

Online: 22th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Cognition, cognitology, general cognitology, linguocognitology cognitive linguistics, linguocognitology, conceptual semantics, linguistic concepts.

ABSTRACT

This article deals with giving explanation of the origin and development of cognitive linguistics, which is a modern branch of linguistics that reveals the relationship between cognition and language.

Cognition is to perceive something. Cognitology is a science on cognition of the world by the help of concepts and can be considered as a new paradigm in the study of language and mind.

General cognitology is a cognitive study of the phenomena, historical changes, and functions of the language without restriction to a particular language or a particular aspect of language. Linguocognitology studies techniques and ways of verbalizing the existing conceptual/ cognitive semantics (concepts) in the mind of language speakers through which the latter cognize the surrounding world and communicate.

Birth of cognitive linguistics and its leading representatives in Europe, USA, Uzbekistan and elsewhere.

Cognitive linguistics was born in America by R. Jackendoff and O. Faunconner. Mostly-renowned representatives of cognitive linguistics are: Langacker, Talmy, Jackendoffs are from America

Kubriyakova, Maslova, Boldiyev, Popov, Sterni, Karasicks are from Russia Safarov, Yusupov, Ashurova, Hoshimov, Mamatovs are from Uzbekistan. Cognitive linguist Margaret Freeman, like Hamilton, uses blending theory, a. k. a. conceptual integration networks (e.g. Fauconnier & Turner, 1998; 2002), to analyse the poetic text and, similarly, she also stresses that by analysing the processes of poetic creation and interpretation the cognitive method reveals explanatory power in a direct way. In a series of interesting moves Freeman demonstrates how the embodied mind is at work when it encounters the shape of the poetic text in Emily Dickinson's hand-written manuscripts compared to their printed variations. This physical basis of understanding is at work on many levels, also in Dickinson's metacognitive question to her editors whether or not her poetry is alive and 'breaths.' Between the lines Freeman also points to a theoretical debt as regards the notion of the embodied mind being

largely claimed by Lakoff & Johnson (1980; 1999) – but without reference to Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology.

And there revealed that this discipline relies on the imagination, knowledge, habits and skills gained while studying such courses as “General linguistics”, “Stylistics and text analysis“, “Lexicology”, “Theory of Translation”, and “Textlinguistics” and aims at further developing them. Cognitive linguistics is closely linked with such contemporary trends of modern linguistics as “Linguopragmatics”, “Linguoculturology“, “Linguoconceptology”, “Linguistic Typology”, “Cognitive Typology”, “Cognitive Stylistics”, “Cognitive phonology”, “Cognitive Morphology”, “Cognitive Lexicology”, “Cognitive Syntax”, “Cognitive Phraseology”, “Textlinguistics” and “Cognitive Textlinguistics”.

The object of study of cognitive linguistics is concepts (conceptual or cognitive semantics) objectivated by verbalizers (of the type: phoneme, morpheme, morphophoneme, lexeme, syntaxeme (phraseme, sentenceme), phraseoeme, texteme (discourseme)). The material of the study of cognitive linguistics is verbalizers (phoneme, morpheme, morphophoneme, lexeme, syntaxeme (phraseme, sentenceme), phraseoeme, texteme (discourseme)) representing various techniques and ways of objectivating existing concepts of the structure of knowledge of the objective world.

Cognitive linguistics emerged from research conducted by prominent scholars working on the West Coast of the United States during the 1970s and 1980s. Most notable among these are Ronald W. Langacker (Langacker 1987–1991), who developed the theory of cognitive grammar (see Cognitive Grammar); George Lakoff (Lakoff 1987), who applied work on categorization to metaphor, lexical semantics, and grammar; and Leonard Talmy (Talmy 2000), who studied the conceptual basis of grammar. These three researchers are widely considered to be the founding fathers of the enterprise. Also foundational were Lakoff and Johnson 1980, which developed conceptual metaphor theory (see Conceptual Metaphor Theory) and Johnson 1987, which developed the theory of image schema (see Image Schema Theory) that grew out of work on conceptual metaphors. Other important work that has proved to be foundational was developed in Fillmore 1982 on frame semantics (see Frame Semantics) and Fillmore, et al. 1988, which provided the basis for the theory of construction grammar (see Construction Grammar). Fauconnier 1994 developed the theory of mental spaces (see Mental Spaces Theory), which later gave rise to conceptual integration theory (see Conceptual Integration Theory).

Cognitive semantics approaches meaning from the perspective of cognitive linguistics. In this framework, language is explained via general human cognitive abilities rather than a domain-specific language module. The techniques native to cognitive semantics are typically used in lexical studies such as those put forth by Leonard Talmy, George Lakoff, Dirk Geeraerts, and Bruce Wayne Hawkins. Some cognitive semantic frameworks, such as that developed by Talmy, take into account syntactic structures as well. Semantics, through modern researchers can be linked to the Wernicke's area of the brain and can be measured using the event-related potential (ERP). ERP is the rapid electrical response recorded with small disc electrodes which are placed on a person's scalp.

Here I am going to give brief information (based on my own translation from the book “Cognitive Linguistics” by Uzbek scholar, Sh. Safarov) of prominent Russian cognitive linguists

of whom contribution was to more extent a prototype to create general and long term knowledge base for interdisciplinary field of linguistics, cognitive linguistics.

There is a useful point in that Cognitive Linguistics is considered as the science in which linguistic competence is well- established and formed. (В.З.Демьянков (1994: 17). In reality, the analysis of means and methods which evaluate linguistic expressions of mental structures are caused in the way of realizing the world in cognitive analysis. Mind consciously perceives the phenomena of the world and the knowledge is accumulated as soon as our imagination cognizes them with mental picture under mind consequently this knowledge is evaluated and gets various characters. And this, in turn, brings out the concepts of different categorization and from different structures. The categorization of concepts basically relies on their styles of linguistic methods. Many researchers on this field are claiming to separate the concepts not only to lexical or phraseologic types but also grammatic (to be more precise, syntactic) types too. (Бабушкин 1996; Волохина, Попова 1999; Langacker 1987).

Concept is a mental structure, it is generality of quant or knowledge in different aspects and different constituents. (Кубрякова и др . 1996: 90). Concepts constitutes the base of various categories which is formed in human mind, and serves as lever long for them.

“Concept as a mental structure, is typical form (type) of mental process. Concept happens as a result of mental process which separates general and distinctive features of collective signs that unite the objective world from identical category.” (Войшвилло 1989: 91).

Yanna Popova stresses how a cognitive approach to language can provide a much needed methodology for literary interpretation, but also how it can be a tool in discussing theories of interpretation. To the background of how New Critics and early structuralists sought to explain and ‘remedy’ ambiguous texts, and how poststructuralists have instead hailed the irreducible nature of such texts, Popova proceeds to James’s *The Figure in the Carpet* and shows in a cognitive stylistic analysis not how to value ambiguity but demonstrates why James’s text is irresolvable. Both non-ironic readings (New Critic; structuralist) and ironic readings (poststructuralism; deconstruction) are possible and supported by James’s text and in a quest for middle ground between objectivism and subjectivism, Popova focuses in on ambiguity as produced by alternative metaphorical conceptualisations. The result of this cognitive mapping is a convincing analysis of the materiality of reading. Uzbek cognitive linguists and their research works on cognitive linguistics (Sh. Safarov, D.U.Ashurova, U.K.Yusupov, A.E. Mamatov, G.M.Hoshimov, et al.); Expressing his personal view on the relation, interrelation and interaction of those new sciences in modern linguistics prof U.K.Yusupov points out that at present there have appeared some new scientific directions like cognitive linguistics, linguo-culturology, culture-oriented linguistics, ethnolinguistics, cultural anthropology, etc. which are all anthropocentral in their orientation and study the interrelation and interaction of language and culture of people, but among them, as he thinks, the most perspective is linguoculturology which, unlike the others, may prove very useful in teaching foreign languages.

New sciences have one and the same subject matter of investigation – interrelation and interaction of (native/foreign) speaker and his language, on the one hand, thinking (thought) and culture, on the other, which results in the cognition of the world (the objective reality).

The latter (cognition) is naturally based on the speaker's conceptsphere (hence is the notion of conceptuality – term due to G.Hoshimov) respectively materialized or objectivized by means of language representants that exist and function in accordance with this or that scope of linguosphere (sphere of languages aquired and llinguality (the complex of knowledge of language(s) of the speaker shaped throughout his life experience).

It is also vital to to take into consideration the linguoculturemes of the aforesaid types when translating them from one language into the other, for care should be taken that there should not be any semantic losses in translation, or else the translation will not be as adequate as it should be. See the cases of linguocultural differences between the linguoculturemes (aunt, амма/хола, дядя, амаки/ тоға) of the compared languages(English and Uzbek/Russian). (G.Hoshimov).

References:

1. Robinson, Peter (2008). Handbook of Cognitive Linguistics and Second Language Acquisition. Routledge. pp. 3–8. ISBN 978-0-805-85352-0.
2. Peeters, Bert (1998). "Cognitive musings". Word. **49** (2): 225–237. doi:10.1080/00437956.1998.11673884.
3. Schwarz-Friesel, Monika (2012). "On the status of external evidence in the theories of cognitive linguistics". Language Sciences. **34** (6): 656–664. doi:10.1016/j.langsci.2012.04.007.
4. Greenwood, John D (1999). "Understanding the 'cognitive revolution' in psychology". Journal of the History of the Behavioral Sciences. **35** (1): 1–22. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1520-6696(199924)35:1<1::AID-JHBS1>3.0.CO;2-4. Retrieved 2020-02-22.

5. Harris, Randy Allen (1995). *The Linguistics Wars*. Oxford: OUP. ISBN 978-0-19-983906-3.
6. Peeters, Bert (2001). "Does cognitive linguistics live up to its name?". In Dirven, René (ed.). *Language and Ideology, Vol.1: Theoretical Cognitive Approaches*. John Benjamins. pp. 83–106. ISBN 978-90-272-9954-3.
7. Marantz, Alec (2005). "Generative linguistics within the cognitive neuroscience of language". *The Linguistic Review*. **22** (2–4): 492–445. CiteSeerX 10.1.1.718.940. doi:10.1515/tlir.2005.22.2-4.429. S2CID 8727463.
8. Nigora, A., Haydarova, U., & Madina, T. (2022, December). METONIMIYANING O 'ZBEK, INGLIZ VA RUS TILLARIDA QO 'LLANILISHI. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 206-210).
9. Turdimatova, M. (2021). SEMANTIC NOTION OF DIMINUTIVES IN THE FORMATION OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(2).
10. Shakhnoza, I., Galimullina, L., & Madina, T. (2022, December). INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE METHOD OF TEACHING GRAMMAR IN THE EFL CLASSROOM. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 167-170).
11. Shakhnoza, I., Markhabo, S., & Madina, T. (2022, December). LINGUISTIC ENVIRONMENT AND ITS FEATURES IN UZBEKISTAN. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 171-174).
12. Xamrakulova, R. (2023). TURLI SOHA VAKILLARIGA CHET TILINI O 'QITISHDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(2 Part 2), 45-49.
13. Turdimatova Madinakhon Ravshanovna. DIFFERENT TYPES OF IRONY IN LITERATURE. Vol. 3 No. 4 (2022): *wos.Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/1234>
14. Turdimatova Madinaxhan Ravshanovna. (2022). THE PERCEPTIVE MEANING IN VERBAL IRONY. *E Conference Zone*, 19–21. Retrieved from <http://econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/295>.
15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6339996> Turdimatova Madina. Kinoyaning ijobiy tanqid orqali ifodalanishi. 02.02.2022. Russia.
16. Abdulakhatovna, K. R. (2022). THE NOTION SPEECH ACTS AND ANALYSES OF THE WORK "A CUP OF TEA" BY KATHERINE MANSFIELD. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(08), 135-140.
17. Abdulaxatovna, X. R. (2022). ABRAHAM LINKOLN IBORALARINING MISOLIDA NUTQNING PSIXOLINGVISTIK KO 'RINISHI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(10), 413-416.
18. Abdulakhatovna, K. R. (2022). DIPLOMATIC DISCOURSE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 18-22.
19. Abdulakhatovna, K. R. (2022). LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 113-118.
20. Ravshanovna, T. M., & Abdulakhatovna, K. R. (2022). Typology. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(12), 101-107.